

LEGAL ANALYSIS OF INVOLVING A MINOR IN ANTI-SOCIAL BEHAVIOR: THE EXPERIENCE OF UZBEKISTAN AND GERMANY

Jienbaeva Salima Asqarovna

2nd year master's student in the specialty "Theory and Practice of Application of Criminal Law" at Karakalpak State University
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INTRODUCTION.

In today's rapidly evolving society, the protection of minors from criminal influence and anti-social behavior remains a pressing legal and social issue. The involvement of minors in illegal activities, immoral acts, or criminal organizations not only threatens their future development but also contributes to the overall rise in juvenile delinquency. Recognizing the seriousness of this issue, many countries, including Uzbekistan and Germany, have established legal frameworks to prevent and penalize such actions.

The legal approaches of Uzbekistan and Germany towards the recruitment of minors into anti-social behavior differ in various aspects, including the definition of offenses, the severity of penalties, and preventive measures. Uzbekistan's legal system emphasizes preventive policies alongside criminal liability, while Germany enforces strict punitive measures complemented by specialized juvenile justice mechanisms.¹

This article aims to analyze and compare the legal provisions in Uzbekistan and Germany concerning the recruitment of minors into anti-social behavior. The study will examine legislative norms, law enforcement practices, and the effectiveness of preventive measures in both countries. Understanding these differences and similarities can provide valuable insights for improving legal policies and ensuring better protection for minors from criminal influences.

¹ O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI KONSTITUTSIYASI (yangi tahrir) 30.04.2023 yil

1-§ The concept and legal analysis of involving minors in antisocial behavior concept and legal analysis

Involving minors in antisocial behavior refers to forcing them into illegal activities or immoral conduct, inciting them to commit crimes, and teaching them to consume alcohol and narcotic substances. These actions are often perpetrated by adults or criminal groups, resulting in the involvement of minors in criminal activities.²

The involvement of minors in antisocial behavior is a complex socio-legal problem, the prevention and combating of which is one of the important tasks of the state. The legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for several types of liability for involving a minor in antisocial behavior, which are applied depending on the severity of the act and the age of the minor.

Antisocial behavior, in general, is actions that contradict the accepted norms and laws of society. In relation to minors, this concept may include the following actions:

- Crimes: Theft, robbery, violence, drug-related crimes, etc.
- Administrative offenses: Petty hooliganism, violation of public order, school evasion, etc..³
- Antisocial behavior: Aggression towards oneself and others, drug use, alcohol consumption, begging, etc..

From a legal point of view, such actions are regulated by special clauses in the criminal codes of Uzbekistan and Germany, which are considered a crime and entail strict criminal liability.

§ 2. Minors in the legislation of Uzbekistan liability for involvement in antisocial actions

In the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the involvement of minors in crime or antisocial behavior is considered a crime. Responsibility for this act is established by the following articles of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

Criminal liability: Minors who have committed serious crimes stipulated by the Criminal Code are subject to criminal liability. They may face lighter punishments, but in severe cases, imprisonment may also be imposed.⁴

Article 127 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan - Involvement of a minor in antisocial behavior Involvement of a minor in the consumption of alcoholic beverages, narcotic drugs and their analogues or substances that are not psychotropic, but affect the mind, committed after the application of administrative penalties for the same actions, —

shall be punishable by a fine in the amount of one hundred to two hundred times the basic calculation amount or by compulsory community service for a term of up to three hundred and sixty hours, or by correctional labor for a term of up to two years, or by restriction of liberty for a term of one to three years, or by imprisonment for a term of three years. Involving a minor in the use of narcotic drugs, their analogues, or psychotropic substances shall be punishable by compulsory community service for a term of three hundred and sixty to four hundred and eighty hours, or by restriction of liberty for a term of three to five years, or by imprisonment for a term of three to five years. Involving a minor in the commission of a

² Rustambayev M.X. O'zbekiston Respublikasi jinoyat huquqi kursi. Tom 3. Maxsus qism. Shaxsga qarshi jinoyatlar. Tinchlik va xavfsizligiga qarshi jinoyatlar. Darslik. 2-nashr, to'ldirilgan va qayta ishlangan – T.: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Milliy gvardiyasi Harbiy-texnik instituti, 2018. – 412 bet.

³ 1.2 S.S.Niyozova Ma'muriy javobgarlik (Umumiy qism) / O'quv qullanma. –T.: TDYU nashriyoti, 2020. bet.

⁴ Jinoyat huquqi.(Umumiy qism) / O'quv qullanma. Ochilov X.R. - Toshkent:Yuridik adabiyotlar Publish,2022-y -176

crime, as well as the actions provided for in the second part of this article: a) by a person who has previously committed any crime related to the illegal circulation of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances; b) against two or more minors; c) committed in educational institutions or other places where students, pupils, and students hold educational, sports or public events, shall be punishable by imprisonment for a term of five to ten years.⁵

The following measures are applied under these articles of the Criminal Code:

- Criminal liability – imprisonment for up to 5 years
- Administrative liability - Fine for inducing minors to use alcohol or tobacco products⁶
- Civil liability - Compensation for material and moral damage caused to the victim

Also, in order to protect minors and protect them from delinquency, the Law "On the Prevention of Neglect and Delinquency among Minors" was adopted in Uzbekistan (Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-263 dated 29.09.2010). This law provides for preventive measures aimed at preventing the involvement of minors in illegal activities.⁷

3§. Liability under German law for involving minors in antisocial activities

In German criminal law, involving minors in crime and causing their moral degradation is also considered a serious crime. These issues are regulated by the German Criminal Code (Strafgesetzbuch - StGB) and the Jugendgerichtsgesetz (JGG).

- § 180 - Incitement of a minor to moral depravity
- § 171 - Violation of parental duties
- § 235 - Illegal removal or concealment of a child
- § 129 - Formation of a criminal group and involvement of minors⁸

According to these articles, the following punishments are established in Germany:

- Criminal liability - imprisonment from 5 to 10 years
- Administrative liability - Fine for selling tobacco or alcohol to minors
- Civil liability - the obligation to compensate for material damage to victims

In Germany, there is a separate juvenile court (Jugendgericht), which adapts sentences for young people and monitors their social rehabilitation.⁹

§ 4. Differences between the legislation of Uzbekistan and Germany:

⁵ O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASINING JINOYAT KODEKSI 22.09.1994 yil

⁶ O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASINING MA'MURIY JAVOGBARLIK TO'G'RISIDAGI KODEKSI 22.09.1994 yil

⁷ "Voyaga yetmaganlar o'rtasida nazoratsizlik va huquqbuzarliklarning profilaktikasi to'g'risida"gi qonun (O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni, 29.09.2010 yildagi O'QRQ-263-son)

⁸ Strafgesetzbuch (StGB) Ausfertigungsdatum: 15.05.1871 Vollzitat: "Strafgesetzbuch in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 13. November 1998 (BGBl. I S. 3322), das zuletzt durch Artikel 2 Absatz 2 des Gesetzes vom 7. November 2024 (BGBl. 2024 I Nr. 351) geändert worden ist"

⁹ Baumgärtel G (1987) Anmerkung zu BGH VI ZR 294/85 vom 1.7.1986. JZ 42: 42

Normative aspects	Uzbekistan	Germany
Involvement of minors in immoral acts	imprisonment for up to 5 years	imprisonment for up to 5-10 years
Coercion of juveniles to crime	Punishment is determined by the Criminal Code.	It is regulated by the Criminal Code and special courts
Special juvenile courts	special courts Special commissions and courts for minors	Special juvenile court (Jugendgericht)
Failure to fulfill parental duty	imprisonment for up to 3 years	Up to 3 years in prison or fine
Involvement of minors in criminal groups	It is regulated by the Criminal Code.	There are strict penalties under the Criminal Code.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan and Germany have a unique approach to protecting minors from antisocial behavior. In Germany, punishments are relatively harsh, and there is a separate judicial system for minors. In Uzbekistan, however, more attention is paid to preventive measures, and special commissions operate to protect minors from crime.

The experience of both countries shows that punishment alone is not enough to protect minors from antisocial behavior, but strengthening preventive measures is also important. Therefore, it is important to study and apply international experience in this area.

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1.Main references

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1.2 S.S.Niyozova Ma'muriy javobgarlik (Umumiy qism) / O'quv qullanma. –T.: TDYU nashriyoti, 2020. bet.

1.3 Jinoyat huquqi.(Umumiy qism) / O'quv qullanma. Ochilov X.R. - Toshkent:Yuridik adabiyotlar Publish,2022-y -176

2.Legal Documents

2.1 O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI KONSTITUTSIYASI (yangi tahrir) 30.04.2023 yil

2.2 O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASINING JINOYAT KODEKSI 22.09.1994 yil

2.3 O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASINING MA'MURIY JAVOBGARLIK TO'G'RISIDAGI KODEKSI 22.09.1994 yil

2.4 "Voyaga yetmaganlar o'rtasida nazoratsizlik va huquqbuzarliklarning profilaktikasi to'g'risida"gi qonun(O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni, 29.09.2010 yildagi O'RQ-263-son)

2.5 Strafgesetzbuch (StGB) Ausfertigungsdatum: 15.05.1871 Vollzitat: "Strafgesetzbuch in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 13. November 1998 (BGBl. I S. 3322), das zuletzt durch Artikel 2 Absatz 2 des Gesetzes vom 7. November 2024 (BGBl. 2024 I Nr. 351) geändert worden ist"

2.6 Gesetz über Ordnungswidrigkeiten (OWiG) OWiG Ausfertigungsdatum: 24.05.1968 Vollzitat: "Gesetz über Ordnungswidrigkeiten in der Fassung der Bekanntmachung vom 19. Februar 1987 (BGBl. I S. 602), das zuletzt durch Artikel 10 des Gesetzes vom 12. Juli 2024 (BGBl. 2024 I Nr. 234) geändert worden ist"

2.7 Baumgärtel G (1987) Anmerkung zu BGH VI ZR 294/85 vom 1.7.1986. JZ 42: 42

